

Package ‘CovidAssociations’

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Type Package

Title Allows data mining of associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid patients

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Description This package contains results of associations between pairs of variables in a large cohort of more than 25 millions of Covid-19 patients from Mexico that were collected between January 2020 and March 2023 by the Mexican Government. Pairs of variables were tabulated into 2 x 2 contingency tables and analyzed by Fisher's exact test. A maximum of 25,820,354 patients have valid (not missing) data in a single comparison. There are 20 dichotomous variables and 25 patient's groups, for a total of 3,899 results (associations). The user can select variable pairs and examine associations among patients groups. Original and recoded data are also available from the Mexican Government and from the author, respectively.

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CovidAssociations-package

Allows data mining of associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid patients

Description

This package contains results of associations between pairs of variables in a large cohort of more than 25 millions of Covid-19 patients from Mexico that were collected between January 2020 and March 2023 by the Mexican Government. Pairs of variables were tabulated into 2 x 2 contingency tables and analyzed by Fisher's exact test. A maximum of 25,820,354 patients have valid (not missing) data in a single comparison. There are 20 dichotomous variables and 25 patient's groups, for a total of 3,899 results (associations). The user can select variable pairs and examine associations among patients groups. Original and recoded data are also available from the Mexican Government and from the author, respectively.

Details

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To use this package you must have one or two variables of interest. You could select such variables by browsing the `data.frame var.desc`. Then you could select either, all or a particular group of patients of interest. Browse the `data.frame came.from.desc` to see the groups available. Having one or two variables of interest in one or more patient groups, you can run the function `isolate.res` to obtain one or more relevant sets of data. Then, by running the function `present.table`, you will obtain detailed information about the results of the 2 x 2 contingency table. See examples below.

Author(s)

Octavio Martinez

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References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

See Also

[var.desc](#), [came.from.desc](#), [isolate.res](#), [present.table](#)

Examples

```
data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)
```

```
# Note: execute the examples one line at the time
# and examine the results presented.
```

```
### 1
# Find which associations exist with "smoking"
# (we will use a single variable in the general
# group of all patients)
temp.1 <- isolate.res(var1="smoking")
nrow(temp.1)
# Now order
temp.1 <- temp.1[order(temp.1$or, decreasing=TRUE),]

# Examine only main variables
# pv = p-value in Fisher's test;
# or = Odds ratio.
temp.1[, 3:5]
# Now, see the table for copd_smoking
# which is the one with a largest association
# (Do not keep the results)
present.table(temp.1[1,])

# Now, let's see the table with the
# smallest "or" (the one with
# smallest Odd Ratio)
present.table(temp.1[19,])

# Now se one that is less significant
# (the one with the largest p-value)
present.table(temp.1[temp.1$pv==max(temp.1$pv),])

# Remove the temporal object created
rm(temp.1)

### 2
# Interested in "asthma" and "hospitalized"
# Assume that you are interested in the
# variables "asthma" and "hospitalized"
# but want to see the general results
# i.e., you will use the default group = "gen.res"

# Isolate the results for those variables:
temp.1 <- isolate.res("asthma", "hospitalized")
temp.1 # See the results (note there is a single row)

# Now:
present.table(temp.1) # presents the table(s)
# The function returned the results invisibly.
# You could keep such results using
temp.2 <- present.table(temp.1)
# Now see:
class(temp.2)
names(temp.2)
temp.2 # Gives all the components of the result

# Remove the previously created objects:
rm(temp.1, temp.2)

### 3
# A more complex example:
# You want to explore the associations between
```

```

# chronic renal problems (which is coded as "chr.renal")
# and "deceased" (patients that were reported as dead).
# but you want to see the relations in all patient groups.

# First isolate the results
temp.1 <- isolate.res("chr.renal", "deceased", group="all")

# Associations in different groups, one per row:
nrow(temp.1)
# Let's order that data.frame by strength of association:
# (which is coded in the variable "or" = Odds Ratio)
temp.1 <- temp.1[order(temp.1$or, decreasing=TRUE), ]
# See the main columns:
# group ("came.from"), p-value (pv) and Odds Ratio (or)
temp.1[, c(10,4,5)] # See the main columns
# We see a large variation in the or:
summary(temp.1$or) # Summary of Odds Ratio (or)

# Now see the table with the less strong association:
present.table(temp.1[temp.1$or==min(temp.1$or), ])
# This corresponds to hospitalized patients.
# Same result will be obtained by:
temp.2 <- temp.1[temp.1$or==min(temp.1$or), ]
# present.table(temp.2)

# Now the case with largest association is in
temp.1[1, ] # Because we ordered the data.frame
# Isolate that single row in an object:
temp.2 <- temp.1[1,] # Only the first row.
# and present the table:
temp.3 <- present.table(temp.2)

# Finally remove the previously created objects
rm(temp.1, temp.2, temp.3)

```

all.res

All results in the package

Description

This data frame contain all the results that can be examined. However, it will be more useful to use the functions provided in the package to select sets of variables within groups of patients to mine this data

Usage

```
data("all.res")
```

Format

A data frame with 3899 observations on the following 18 variables.

n.tab a numeric vector indexing the table from which the data came

n.c.row a numeric vector

`n.c.col` a numeric vector
`name.row` a character vector with the name of the variable used for the rows in the table
`name.col` a character vector with the name of the variable used for the columns in the table
`name.tab` a character vector with the name of the table
`pv` a numeric vector containing the p-value from the Fisher's test of the table
`or` a numeric vector containing the Odds Ratio from the Fisher's test of the table
`LL` a numeric vector containing the 95% Lower Limit of the Odds Ratio from the Fisher's test of the table
`UL` a numeric vector containing the 95% Upper Limit of the Odds Ratio from the Fisher's test of the table
`or2` a numeric vector containing the value of the inverse of the Odds Ratio when that quantity is smaller than one. Otherwise `or2` is identical to `or`
`dir` a character vector (not relevant for the user)
`came.from` a character vector with the name of the group from which the table was obtained
`tab.file` a character vector (not relevant for the user)
`a` a numeric vector with the number of patients that fulfill the criteria in the upper left hand side corner of the table
`b` a numeric vector with the number of patients that fulfill the criteria in the upper right hand side corner of the table
`c` a numeric vector with the number of patients that fulfill the criteria in the lower left hand side corner of the table
`d` a numeric vector with the number of patients that fulfill the criteria in the lower right hand side corner of the table

Details

`all.res` is not in general directly useful to the user; you must use the functions `isolate.res` and `present.table` to obtain meaningful outcomes.

Source

Original data obtained from <https://www.gob.mx/salud/documentos/datos-abiertos-bases-historicas-direc> March 2023.

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

Examples

```

data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)

# A vector with all the names of the variables
sort(union(all.res$name.row, all.res$name.col))

# A vector with the names of the patient groups

```

```
sort(unique(all.res$came.from))

# A summary of p-value (pv) and Odds Ratio (or)
summary(all.res[,7:8])
```

came.from.desc	<i>Names and descriptions of patient's groups</i>
----------------	---

Description

This data.frame gives the names of 25 patients groups that were determined to from different attributes to be analyzed separately. It can be used to direct the search of interesting association between variables

Usage

```
data("came.from.desc")
```

Format

A data frame with 25 observations on the following 3 variables.

came.from a character vector containing the coded name of each one of the 25 patient's groups

n.res a numeric vector containing the number of results (number of 2x2 contingency tables) that exist within each patient group

Description a character vector containing a brief description of the profile of the patients included in the group

Details

This data.frame is useful to restrict the result search to particular groups of patients

Source

Original data obtained from <https://www.gob.mx/salud/documentos/datos-abiertos-bases-historicas-direc> March 2023.

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

Examples

```
data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)

# A summary of the number of 2x2 tables per group
summary(came.from.desc$n.res)

# Groups which description begins with "Female"
came.from.desc[substring(came.from.desc$Description, 1,6)=="Female",]
```

```
# Groups of patients per Age group  
came.from.desc[substring(came.from.desc$Description, 1,9)=="Age group",]
```

expected	<i>Obtains the expected value for a contingency table</i>
----------	---

Description

This function takes an $r \times c$ contingency table and obtains the value expected under the null hypothesis of independence for such table. It is used by the function `present.table()` and is not directly needed by the user

Usage

```
expected(x)
```

Arguments

`x` A contingency table (matrix) of any order

Value

A matrix (contingency table) of the same order than the input with the expected values

Note

The function does not allow missing values (NA)

Author(s)

Octavio Martinez

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

See Also

[present.table](#)

Examples

```
data(all.res)  
data(var.desc)  
data(came.from.desc)  
  
# An extreme 2x2 contingency table with n=10  
matrix(c(10,0,0,10), nrow=2, ncol=2)  
# The expected value of that table  
expected(matrix(c(10,0,0,10), nrow=2, ncol=2))  
# You could also try:
```

```

# fisher.test(matrix(c(10,0,0,10), nrow=2, ncol=2))
# to see why this table is "extreme"

# Other example with a 3 x 2 table
matrix(c(10,0,0,10, 3, 5), nrow=3, ncol=2)
# The expected value of that table
expected(matrix(c(10,0,0,10, 3, 5), nrow=3, ncol=2))

# A matrix with the package data.
present.table(do.printing=FALSE)[[1]]
# The expected value of that table
expected(present.table(do.printing=FALSE)[[1]])

# If you wish run
# present.table()
# to see full results.

```

isolate.res

Isolate one or more results to be examined

Description

This function produces a data.frame including results with specified variables and groups of patients. The user can select between combinations of pairs of 20 different variables and one of the 25 groups of patients. There is also the option to output the results for all 25 groups. Each row in the output can then be examined using the function `present.table()`

Usage

```
isolate.res(var1 = "asthma", var2 = NULL, only.significant = FALSE, alpha = 0.01, group = "gen.res")
```

Arguments

var1	Must be one of the coded names of variables in the <code>var.desc</code> data frame. See <code>var.desc\$Name</code> for the list of acceptable values.
var2	If NULL then all the 19 variables other than the value in <code>var1</code> are included. Otherwise it must be one of the coded names of variables in the <code>var.desc</code> data frame, different to <code>var1</code> . See <code>var.desc\$Name</code> for the list of acceptable values.
only.significant	A logic variable. If TRUE then only results with a p-value equal or smaller than the parameter <code>alpha</code> , which regulates the probability of Error Type I. If FALSE then no filtering is performed and all results are output.
alpha	A threshold for the maximum value of p (p-value) for the results that will be output when <code>only.significant = TRUE</code> . This parameter allow the exclusion of not-significant results.
group	A group of patients from which results are desired. The default, "gen.res2", implies that the output will have results in the full set of patients. The value "all" will give results from all the groups that exist. Otherwise, valid values for this parameters are the ones in the variable <code>came.from</code> of the <code>came.from.desc</code> data frame. To see all 25 acceptable values for this parameter type <code>came.from.desc\$came.from</code> .

Value

A data.frame with 15 variables that will be a subset of all.res, determined by the input parameters. Each row of the output can then be the input to function present.table for further examination.

Author(s)

Octavio Martinez

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

See Also

[present.table](#), [var.desc](#), [came.from.desc](#), [all.res](#)

Examples

```
data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)

# If you want to see the options for parameters
# var1 and var2 type "var.desc$Name"
# To see the options for the parameter group
# type "came.from.desc$came.from"

# Result for "pneumonia" and "pregnancy"
# in the group of all patients
# Note: Parameter group = "gen.res"
# which is the default.
isolate.res("pneumonia", "pregnancy")

# Same variables but now in a specific
# group of male patients
# group="ma.res"
isolate.res("pneumonia", "pregnancy", group="ma.res")

# Now, let's obtain the results but in all
# different groups of patients where there are
# data for those two variables:
# group="all"
temp.1 <- isolate.res("pneumonia", "pregnancy", group="all")
# How many results?
nrow(temp.1)
temp.1$came.from # Patients groups
summary(temp.1$or) # Summary of Odds Ratios
summary(temp.1$pv) # Summary of p-values

# Now, assume that you want all relations
# between "pregnancy" and any other variables
# in all possible patient's groups
# (let var2 as "NULL" -the default)
temp.1 <- isolate.res("pneumonia", group="all")
```

```
nrow(temp.1) # How many results?
# Tabulate those results by
# relation ("name.tab")
table(temp.1$name.tab)
# now by patient group ("came.from")
table(temp.1$came.from)
summary(temp.1$or) # Summary of Odds Ratios
# Which relation has the largest Odds Ratio?
temp.1[temp.1$or == max(temp.1$or),]
# And which has the smallest Odds Ratio?
temp.1[temp.1$or == min(temp.1$or),]
# Remove defined object
rm(temp.1)
```

present.table	<i>Presents tables for a specific result</i>
---------------	--

Description

This function takes as input a single row of the data.frame output by the function `isolate.res()` and print tables useful for interpretation. Also it invisibly output the results. Used mainly by its side effects (printing tables and results).

Usage

```
present.table(the.row = isolate.res(var1 = "deceased", var2 = "gender")[1, ], do.printing = TRUE)
```

Arguments

<code>the.row</code>	A single row of a data.frame output by function <code>isolate.res</code>
<code>do.printing</code>	Logical parameter. If TRUE (the default) output is printed. If FALSE there is not printing.

Value

The function invisibly returns a list with the following components:

<code>raw.tab</code>	A matrix with the raw data that were analyzed
<code>expected</code>	A matrix with the values expected for the cells under the null hypothesis of independence
<code>raw.tab.wt</code>	A matrix with the raw data that were analyzed, but including the totals
<code>rel.fre</code>	A matrix with the relative frequencies of the cells
<code>cond.row.giv.col</code>	A matrix with the conditional probabilities of rows given the columns
<code>cond.col.giv.row</code>	A matrix with the conditional probabilities of columns given the rows
<code>results.fisher.test</code>	Numeric. A vector with the Odds Ratio and p-value from the Fisher's test
<code>the.row</code>	A data frame with the row that was input to the function

Note

The function is used mainly by the its side effect (printing); you do not need to assign the result if no further analyses will be performed.

Author(s)

Octavio Martinez

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

See Also

[isolate.res](#), [var.desc](#), [came.from.desc](#), [all.res](#)

Examples

```
data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)

# First, let's see the result of running
# present.table with the defaults, which are
# the.row=isolate.res("deceased", "gender")[1,]
present.table()
# You could also avoid printing and assign the
# result to an object; say:
temp.1 <- present.table(do.printing=FALSE)
# You could see the results:
temp.1
# Remove that object
rm(temp.1)

# Let's run a more complex example.
# Assume that you are interested in
# data-mining relations of "obesity"
# in all the data available.
# First obtain a data.frame with all
# relevant results:
temp.1 <- isolate.res("obesity", group="all")
nrow(temp.1)

# See some statistics
summary(temp.1$or) # Summary of Odds Ratios
summary(temp.1$pvalue) # Summary of p-values

# Now, select some interesting cases
temp.1.min.or <- temp.1[temp.1$or==min(temp.1$or), ]
nrow(temp.1.min.or)

# Now, you can see the details with
present.table(temp.1.min.or)
temp.1.max.or <- temp.1[temp.1$or==max(temp.1$or), ]
```

```
# and examine the results:
present.table(temp.1.max.or)

# Final remove the temporal objects
rm(temp.1, temp.1.max.or, temp.1.min.or)
```

var.desc

Variables in the results

Description

This data.frame presents the names, abbreviations, category and description of all the 20 variables present in the results (all.res). The var.desc data frame is useful to select variable pairs which results want to be studied

Usage

```
data("var.desc")
```

Format

A data frame with 20 observations on the following 4 variables.

Name a character vector with the names of the variables in the package

Abbr a character vector with a two character abbreviation for the names of the variables in the package

Category a character vector with the assigned category of the variable, either "Attribute" or "Co-morbidity"

Description a character vector with a short description of the nature of the variable

Source

Original data obtained from <https://www.gob.mx/salud/documentos/datos-abiertos-bases-historicas-direc> March 2023.

References

O. Martinez (in preparation). Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients

Examples

```
data(all.res)
data(var.desc)
data(came.from.desc)

# Gives a summary:
str(var.desc)

# The names of all 20 variables:
var.desc$Name
# Note: These names can be used as parameters the function
# "isolate.res" to determine which variables will be studied.
```

```
# The following variables are attributes:
var.desc$Name[var.desc$Category=="Attribute"]
# while the remaining 10 are putative comorbidities:
var.desc$Name[var.desc$Category=="Comorbidity"]

# To look for a row with a specific name
# (as an example)
var.desc[var.desc$Name=="copd",]
```

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